

Strategic Change Management in Human Resources and Organisational Psychology: A Case Study of Alveena Events Abuja, Nigeria

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Abstract:- In the present environment, the company's deals with the different types of issues due to which they need to bring the change in their processes. It became essential for the company to follow the change management structure. Selected company Alveena Events also need change within their organisation which is discussed. The findings show that the company deals with issues like an operational issue, human resource issues, lack of audience engagement and others. This made them bring the change within the organisation. It has been found that different factors drive the change which includes market condition, technology and social elements. Resource implication is required to attain success. The discussion for the change management models which include Lewin's change management model and Prosci's ADKAR model has been done. The relevance of the model for the Alveena Events Company has been discussed in the report. The findings show Change Management Strategy involving Stakeholders and Overcoming Resistance for the company is discussed.

I. INTRODUCTION

Change management is considered as the systemic approach that allows dealing with the transformation within the organisation goals, technologies as well as the processes. The report aims to analyse the change within the organisation. The company Alveena Events, Nigeria is selected for analysing the change and issues that they are facing related to change. The discussion about the major issues linked to the strategic change that is likely to happen within the company is selected. Along with this, different types of change models are adopted which will contribute in bringing the change within the business unit. It is reflected that organisation can lead its stakeholders in adopting as well as developing the strategy which is needed for bringing change. The implementation of the chosen change within the company is also discussed in the report.

II. OVERVIEW OF THE COMPANY

Alveena Events is a specialist in the event decoration, planning as well as the coordination for the different wedding & events. The company is a specialist in the planning, decorating as well as coordinating the different event and wedding in different Nigerian cities. The company work directly with the different clients to orchestrate this momentous event to the finest detail which reflects personal style as well as their signature (Baby Migo, 2019). The

vision of our company is to plan the event in Nigeria in an effective manner. The mission of the company is to offer excellent management services in the professional as well as inconsistent manner. In the research, this has been witnessed that most of the people believe that event planning is a simple thing. However, the reality of the event planning is very different. The company is majorly depended on their event planners who can contribute in offering the successful events. Alveena Events provide support to the companies, individuals, family and others in organising the event.

III. BACKGROUND TO CHANGE

With the evolution of time, there is a need for change within every company for continuous improvement for the revenue as well as for client satisfaction. Alveena Events is one of the known event company and it's become difficult for the company to deal with the competitors who can influence the working of the company (Carnall, 2018). Along with this, the change can place within the organisation as this is the only way through which operations of the company will get change. The company has brought the changes in their company by bringing photography facility to its clients in the venue. It has been determined that Alveena Events deals with the different operational issues due to which they need to bring the IT system that helps in managing all the departments. Apart from this, they deal with the issue of managing the human resources in an effective manner which indirectly influence their performance as well as chances of successful events (My Guide, 2019). Alveena Events Company is not able to attain the high attention of the audience due to which they don't get secured sponsors as well as partners. This issue can be reduced by increasing awareness among people with the effective use of technology. Apart from it, other issues of the company can be resolved with the help of the proper use of technology and software. The entire issues can be responded by the company by implementing the new IT system which will help them to perform effectively.

- **Objective:** The objective of the change is to bring the new IT system within Alveena Events to deal with the issues.

IV. NEED FOR CHANGE IN THE ORGANIZATION

- **Meeting the expectations:** -In the dynamic environment, there is a need for change within the organisation because the needs and expectations of the clients related to the events are increasing. The event planners need to be effective enough and also they

should come up with creative ideas. It has been witnessed that event planner need to bring the new ideas because every time the expectations of the clients increase because they want to maintain their status in front of their relatives and friends (Swaim,2014). Thus, this shows that Alveena Events works with the motive so that they can meet the expectations and makes them contact again for similar or better outcomes.

- **Audience engagement:** - Alveena Events wants to bring improvement in the audience engagement which makes the company bring the change within the organisation. This audience engagement requires change and after that change, it will allow the company to attain a high amount of revenue (Hayes, 2018). The audience engagement will also lead to the rise in mouth publicity which enhances the Alveena Events audience and image in the market.
- **Change is required for grabbing new growth opportunities:** - In the research, this has been determined that change is essential for the company as this will bring the new opportunities for the company (Harding, 2017). The company will get new contracts from the customers and they will be able to generate the brand image in the Nigeria market. This will allow the company to expand its business in different areas, countries and nations which will make them a global event company.
- **Need change for Diversifying:** - Alveena Events need change to diversify their operations because they are providing the services for the limited event only. It has been found that they should organise the events for the celebrity and other Nigeria events which are done on the national level only (Galli, 2018). This will make the company diversify in terms of the event that they are conducting.

V. FACTORS THAT DRIVE THE NEED FOR STRATEGIC CHANGE

Many factors will drive the change within the organisation. It is essential to determine the change which is required to be undertaken by the company. Further, numerous companies form the structures as well as processes through which they can bring the change within the organisation. The factors that majorly lead to the change within the organisation include the external factors and internal factors (Cole-Ingait, 2019). In this, the external factors comprise of the operations that are outside of the organisation and can affect the business. On the other hand, the internal factors are those that drive from the management and operations of the company.

VI. MARKET COMPETITION

It has been found that Alveena Events is unique décor as well as the management event service company with the creative innovation through the different layers of colours and beautiful floral display textures. The company is specialised in forming a highly customized floor with the flowery pattern and high-end design at the event venue. Other companies are giving the tough competition to a company which include Zapphaire Event, Trendy Beevents,

IPC Events and many others. Zapphaire Event is most sought-after celebrity wedding as well as planning company in Nigeria since the year 2003 (Nielsen Company, 2019). The company is majorly known for the detail as well as the quality service that emphasis on special events, wedding and other corporate events. These sorts of competitors make the company bring changes in their company. This has been found that every competitor of the company has some of the speciality. Trendy Beevents is one of the event companies who are competing in the market and they are offering unique themes as well as creating layouts to their clients. Thus, this will attract the customer who wants to present themselves as best but then they deal with the issue of quality.

VII. TECHNOLOGICAL CHANGES

Strategic change is essential for Alveena Events as through this change they can come up with the different issues which they are facing. Technology has transformed the events industry form the past 10 years. It has been found that the biggest change that took place is related to the way of organising, experience and measures the event success and the changing nature as well as the format of the events. Thus, technology change is considered as one of the major factors that drive the change (Jayatilleke and Lai, 2018). The advances in technology have a huge impact on the working of the event planning company. Introduction of the virtual reality as well as the audience tools showcased from the outset that have now become standard practice at the events. This technology makes the company allow the customers so that they can conceptualise their ideas which solve the issue of the company as they get the idea for the event that customer want. The development in technology is growing due to which event companies need to bring the changes in their system. The new technology development is one of the factors that drive the strategic change within Alveena Events. It has been found that development has been taken place in event automation tools, data security, wearable technology, facial recognition, virtual and augmented Reality and project mapping and many others.

VIII. CHANGE IN THE SOCIAL NEEDS OF CUSTOMERS

Social factors are considered as one of the external factors that drive change within Alveena Events. These factors majorly include the change in needs and preferences of the customers present within the environment. In the current environment, the advancement in the technology will make the customers bring the change in their demands towards the event management companies for the different types of events. The customers demand different types of events which include different format because they belong to different cultures. It has been determined that West African nation of Nigeria is comprised of among 250 and 400 ethnic groups but in the entire population there are 60% of the people are those who belong to the major groups that are Hausa, Igbo, Yoruba and Fulani. Nigerian people follow their traditions within their nation and according to their culture, the events are organised by the people present in the country. In the wedding event of Nigeria, there is a formal

introduction ceremony that takes place at the bride to be home (Every culture, 2019). The bride's family accepts the proposal as well as the special food which is served that showed hope after the marriage. Thus, the wedding event will be organised in the country as per the culture of Nigeria. It has been witnessed that there are a different number of people who belongs to different culture due to which there is need of change as Events Company need to offer the services as per the needs of customers.

In case, the customers are asking for the event of the wedding then the need to design and work as per the bride's family in which they can conduct that event. However, there is a possibility that people might demand the different things that are related to their culture. To meet the needs of the customers as well as their expectations the company need to bring the change in their operations, processes and procedure (My Guide, 2019). The events which are generally organised by the Nigerian people include names and naming ceremonies, social youth programme, best of worship, Africa youth leadership and many others. It has been found that these programmes are organised by the Alveena Events. Thus, this shows that the changing needs of the customers due to cultural and social elements make the company bring the change in their operations.

IX. RESOURCE IMPLICATIONS FOR NOT RESPONDING TO THESE CHANGES

It has been determined that there will be the presence of the high implications on the company operations as well as the business if the resources of the Alveena Events do not respond according to the change (Tsaousis and Vakola, 2018). The resources of the company include the staff, IT infrastructure, different departments as well as event planning team. Thus, it has been found that the implications of not responding to the change are given below:

- Lack of IT infrastructure within the Alveena EventsCompany will lead to difficulty for the company in planning the new IT system. The company need the proper infrastructure of IT so that they can bring the change within the company.
- If the departments of the company are not able to communicate and co-ordinate in any of the events then they will not be able to provide their involvement in the implementation of the new system to deal with issues (Simon and Harden, 2019). Along with this, the IT team of Alveena Events will not be able to attain the set deadlines which lead to the impact on business. Further, the lack of involvement will also affect the cost of the entire project of a new IT system.
- If the event planning team is not able to conduct the programming related to the new IT system then they will be able to fail. The change which is expected will find the resistance which will affect the operations of the entire business. However, the company always focuses on the event programming team because it is the base for the company as according to this the company can perform the operations.
- The lack of skills, experience and motivation among the staff affects the implementation of the new system within Alveena Events. The impact will be one the

quality as well as planning of the project completion (Tang, 2019). The employees will not give their maximum efforts to bring change and they can resist to the change which will take place due to which the new IT system will not be able to set.

- The lack of training in the Alveena EventsCompany for the IT tools will affects the company as they will not be able to attain the benefit out of it. However, this is the fact that training is essential to be conducted as it contributes effectively in getting the work done.
- The financial resource is essential to be maintained by the company for bringing any kind of change (Thomas and Hardy, 2011). If in case, the company is dealing with the financial loss then there is lack of possibility for the new system of IT. The financial feasibility is essential to check by the company for the new IT system that deals with different issues. However, this has been determined that Alveena Events has a strong financial background due to which they can maintain the new IT system if they implement the same effectively.

X. CHANGE MANAGEMENT MODELS

In the literature, this has been witnessed that different researchers have presented their models in which they have brought the way for the businesses to bring the change. Out of numerous models, the two models are discussed below which include Lewin's Change Management Model and ADKAR model.

A. Lewin's Change Management Model

Kurt Lewin developed a change model which majorly includes the three steps that are unfreezing, changing and refreezing. For Lewin, the process of change entails forming the perception that change is required then moving towards the new as well as the desired level of behaviour and solidifying the new behaviour (Cummings, Bridgman and Brown, 2016). The theory is consists of three distinct and vital stages which include unfreezing, moving to a new level or changing and refreezing. The below given is the explanation of the three stages of the model.

- **Unfreezing:** -The unfreezing stage of the model include the finding a method of making is practically possible for the people to let go of an out-dated pattern that was counterproductive in some or other way (Hossan, 2015).
- **Moving to a new level:** - This stage involves the process of the change in feelings, thoughts, behaviour or all the three that is in some way more productive.
- **Refreezing:** - The stage of refreezing shows establishing the change as a new habit so that it converts into the standard operating procedure (Dawson, 2019). Without this stage, it becomes easy to backslide into the old ways.

B. Prosci's ADKAR Model

The name of ADKAR is considered as an acronym is based on the different five building blocks that can bring successful change. ADKAR model letters stand for Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability and Reinforcement (Boca, 2013). This model is used by the company to bring the change successful in meeting the needs.

- Awareness: - It includes the need for the change
- Desire: - To participate and support the change
- Knowledge: - On how to change (Wong, et al 2019)
- Ability: - To implement the necessary skills and behaviours
- Reinforcement: - To sustain the change.

XI. THE RELEVANCE OF MODELS IN THE CHOSEN ORGANIZATION

A. Lewin's Change Management Model on Alveena Events

Alveena Events model is relevant to Lewin's Change Management Model which is presented below: -

- **Unfreezing:** - This initial stage of the change helps the Alveena Events to accept that change is required to break down the existing status quo before they can build up the new way of operating the operations for the event. The company is dealing with the operational issue, human resource issues, lack of audience engagement and others due to which change is required. Further, these issues affect the revenue of the company due to which stakeholders of a company are getting affected (Hussain et al, 2018). The major stakeholders of the company are the CEO, investors, clients, suppliers, managers, staff and many others. Out of these stakeholders of the company, investors will not get the sufficient interest due to lack of revenue. Thus, considering the interest and management of the stakeholders the decision for the change is taken by the company. For bringing the new IT system, Alveena Events Company needs to eliminate the existing IT system because that system is not effective in resolving the issues which are faced by Alveena Events. When the company will eliminate the existing system then they will find the resistance from the employees of different departments involved in the event. The staff involved in the event will present the new ways to deal with the same but it will include their comfort.
- **Moving to a new level:** -In this stage, the change will take place which contributes effectively in resolving the level of uncertainty (Shirey, 2013). The company look for the new ways to bring start with and this includes new direction for Alveena Events. There is a possibility that the staff of Alveena Events will take time to become normal. The company needs to make its employees aware that this change will resolve the issues and offer the benefits not only in terms of revenue but also for successful events. Time and communication are considered as the two keys that lead to the success of the change that is required to occur. Employees of a company need the time to understand the different changes and its need within the company. Alveena Events will make their employees understand about the need for a new IT system which contributes to connect to the company. At this stage, the change of the new IT system will take place within Alveena Events.
- **Refreeze:** -In this stage, changes are taking shape as well as people have embraced the new ways of performing the work within the company. The sign of the refreeze structure includes a stable organisation chart and the consistent job descriptions. This stage helps the employees and organisation internalize the changes. Alveena Events Company is going to celebrate

the success that is present behind the change which helps the people for the closure (Kaminski, 2011). The new IT system is the change that took place and offers the benefit to the company in making the events successful. Further, the company will be able to deal with the major challenges which are faced by them. Leaders of the event are effective they become successful in bringing the change. Besides, the training and education will be provided to the employees who help them to apply the change within their operations.

B. Prosci's ADKAR Model on Alveena Events

Alveena Events model is relevant to Prosci's ADKAR Model which is presented below: -

- **Awareness:** -Alveena Events Company will become aware of the fact about the issues that are majorly present within the company. The awareness about the issues is essential as solving these issues will help the company in bringing the new system (Karambelkar and Bhattacharya, 2017). The issues of an operational issue, human resource issues, lack of audience engagement and others affect the company to the most. According to the issues, the company needs to find the best options through which they can come out of the issue. Alveena Events finds that the new IT system will contribute in resolving the issues which are faced by a company that affects the operations of the company. However, Alveena Events need to be aware of the reasons due to which change is required within the company.
- **Desire:** - Alveena Events Company desires to communicate with the company to resolve the issues. The company want to address the different fears which are faced by them related to the operations of the company (Wong, Lacombe, Keller, Joyce, and O'Malley, 2019). However, the company needs to determine the major risks that are involved in the operations of the business. Alveena Events will communicate for introducing the new IT system within the organisation.
- **Knowledge:** - The knowledge stage of the model is implemented by Alveena Events in which they learn the new technical skills that help them in adopting the new IT system. The learning among the team is essential because without any learning of the IT system Alveena Events Company will not be able to apply the change (Shah, 2014). Thus, it leads to the impact on the possibility of events to become successful. Moreover, Alveena Events Company includes different departments who share the information and accordingly they set the reasonable targets.
- **Action:** - The action includes the activities of Alveena Events Company for bringing the change. The company will take the necessary license for the new IT system and according to that, they adjust their entire processes.
- **Reinforcement:** - This stage allows the Alveena Events Company to engage the new IT system with the different employees present in the market (Kuipers et al, 2014). The company will learn from their early mistakes that are done by them. However, new IT system will lead to the success for the company and they can attain the high amount of revenue.

XII. CHANGE MANAGEMENT STRATEGY INVOLVING STAKEHOLDERS AND OVERCOMING RESISTANCE

A. Change Management Strategy involving Stakeholders

The company always involve the stakeholders while taking the strategic decision that will always be the person who is enthusiastic about the change and remains ready to adopt the same. There will be some who will be reluctant at the initial moment and there will be personnel who will be putting the resistance towards the change. The stakeholder's theory of the management is used by the Alveena Events Company while bringing the change (Chebbi, Yahiaoui, Sellami, Papasolomou and Melanthiou, 2019).

The below given is the change management strategy that includes stakeholders.

- **Leverage strategies:** - These strategies are defined and planned for the persons who are considered as the early adopters and remain ready to accept the change. The support and influence have the vital importance and this is the reasons due to which they develop their cooperation as well as support to influence the mind-set of any reluctant for accepting the change.
- **Outplacement strategy:** - For the concerned strategy, high influential resistant laggards, as well as virulent, is considered as one who is majorly focused. The people are offered with an opportunity to reflect and accept their commitment towards the entire change process (Langroodi and Staub-French, 2012). However, if they still don't get agree to adopt the change and they are unwilling to accept then they are allocated with the unambiguous consequences.
- **Engagement strategy:** - The engagement strategy majorly focuses on the key stakeholders and other people who lead to the major influence. The strategy is required to be adopted by Alveena Events with the motive to convert those who adopters as well as influencers. Further, they utilized as well as leverage their influence on those people who are with fewer interest commitments.
- **Containment strategies:** - This strategy majorly emphasizes on the people who are considered as the resistant laggard and with these they are not ready to accept the change (Schridde, 2019). The people are the one who has high skills, experience and competence and they are the one who still contributes to change the entire process.

B. Overcoming Resistance to change

It is considered as one of the major parts that generally takes place in the entire change management process. It is something which can have positive as well as a negative influence on the company. Kotter & Schlesinger define the importance of strategy which is essential to handle the resistance within the company (Clay, 2017). The principles as per the theory are stated below: -

- **Education and communication:** - The proper education, as well as communication with the concerned stakeholder for the change, their misconceptions as well as the confusion, can be sorted out without which they are full of worries as well as questions. Alveena Events

Company employees will accept the change once they get aware about the change.

- **Participation and involvement:** - The strategy is required to be devised as it facilitates the involvement as well as the participation of the different stakeholders within the process of change. It offers the motivation as well as a sense of involvement that makes them believe that they are part of the change that is taking place within the company due to which they don't show resistance.
- **Negotiation and agreement:** - The strategic change within the company brings lots of things for the stake (Appelbaum, Habashy, Malo and Shafiq, 2012). Alveena Events Company can form the agreement among their entire stakeholders which helps them to move towards the change through the proper negotiation.
- **Facilitation and support:-** By facilitating as well as supporting the employees who are motivating as well as initiating the changes help on reducing the resistance to change. The level of motivation increases and boosts the confidence which brings the high chances of the change.

XIII. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

At the end of the report, this is concluded that change management is essential for every company who is operating in the dynamic market. Alveena Events will bring the change in the market with the motive to get success in the events which are organised by them. The report shows that need for change by the Alveena Events. Along with this, it shows the different factors that lead to a change in the market and influences the company to bring change. The resource implication is essential for the successful change by the company. The discussion of the change model has been done which include discussion about Lewin's change management model and Prosci's ADKAR model. These change management models are applied to the company Alveena Events with the motive to bring the change within the company in an effective manner. Further, there is a discussion about change management strategy involving stakeholders and overcoming resistance. Overall, this can be said that the report support to involve the different stakeholders and various strategies to get engaged in the entire change process. It is essential to bring the change process which leads to the success at the organisational level. The implementation of the strategic change management needs further investigation with the motive to accomplish the effectiveness in terms of the business development from the implementation.

It is suggested to Alveena Events Company to form the communication strategies which is essential while communicating for the need of change within the company. Along with this, this communication strategy contributes effectively in improving the resistance level of the employees. Further, it is suggested to the company to appoint the expert who can manage the change which is required within the organisation. This will help the company in applying the change management theory for attaining success.

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